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SONNET – SOCIAL INNOVATION IN ENERGY TRANSITIONS

Co-creating a rich understanding of the diversity, processes, contributions, success and future potentials of social innovation in the energy sector

D6.1 (D24): EU and SIE goal alignment map

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Executive Summary

Based on a survey with SIE-representatives, field-actors and researchers we have evaluated to what extend the aims of SIE-initiatives are aligned with the goals of EU energy policy.

We find that there is a strong support among SIE-initiatives for the EU-aims of increased renewables production and reduced greenhouse gas emissions. The other EU-aims which we tested were perceived by our survey respondents as less important than the SIE-initiatives own aims.

Regarding the correlation between importance ratings for different aims, most aims were positively correlated. One reason for this could be that some of these aims are fairly similar concepts (such as “energy efficiency” and “reduced energy consumption”) or that there are synergies between these aims (such as in case of “regional renewables projects” and “knowledge transfer”).

Table of Contents

1	Context	4
1.1	Introduction	4
1.2	Objectives of WP6.....	4
1.3	Definition of key concepts	4
2	Method	6
2.1	Data Collection.....	6
2.2	Data Analysis	8
3	Results	9
3.1	Average importance of all aims	9
3.2	Average importance of EU-aims per SIE-field	10
3.3	Correlations between importance of aims.....	11
3.3.1	EU-aims.....	12
3.3.2	EU-aims and SIE-aims	13
3.3.3	SIE-aims	14
3.4	Correlation of aim importance rating by different respondent types.....	15
4	Limitations	16
5	Conclusions	17
	Annex 1: EC Summary Requirements	18
	Annex 2: Reviewed Literature Sources	19
	Annex 3: Extended List of Aims	23
	Annex 4: Average importance per country	24
	Annex 5: WP6 Methodological Guidelines	25
1	EMPIRICAL FOCUS OF WP 6 AND KEY CONCEPTS	27
1.1	Objectives of WP6.....	27
1.2	Definition of key concepts	27
1.3	Main links with other work packages.....	28
2	PRACTICALITIES	29
2.1	Partner roles.....	29
2.2	Budget.....	31
2.3	Timeline	31
2.4	Contact point	31

3	DATA GATHERING PROCESS.....	32
4	DATA GATHERING INSTRUMENTS.....	34
4.1	Survey 1: Aims and Contributions	36
4.1.1	Survey 1 Version 1: Researchers and SIE-representatives	37
4.1.2	Survey 1 Version 2: Field-actors	41
4.2	Survey 2: SMART indicators and output measures.....	45
4.3	Survey 3: SIE-participant views	54
5	EVALUATION METHODS	63
5.1	Averages and Rankings	63
5.2	Pairwise correlations.....	65
5.3	Multi-variate regressions	68
6	WORK PLAN AND KEY DATES	69

Figures

Figure 1: Average importance of aims for SIE-initiatives.	9
Figure 2: Heatmap of correlations between importance rankings for A) EU-aims, B) EU- and SIE-aims and C) SIE-aims, which are significant at p=10% level.....	11
Figure 3: Average importance rating by participants vs. researchers (left), participants vs. field-actors (center) and researchers vs. field-actors (right) for each aim	15

Tables

Table 1: Consolidated list of aims.....	6
Table 2: Average importance of aims per SIE-field.....	10
Table 3: Correlation of importance between different EU goals	12
Table 4: Correlation of importance between EU-aims and SIE-aims.....	13
Table 5: Correlation of importance between different SIE-aims	14
Annex 5:	
Table 1: Persons involved in WP6.	30
Table 2: Data gathering process for WP6.....	32
Table 3: Overview of surveys used in WP6.....	34
Table 4: Work-plan and key dates.....	69

1 CONTEXT

1.1 Introduction

SONNET aims to create an inter- and transdisciplinary understanding of the diversity and processes of social innovations in the energy sector (SIE). It assesses - critically and reflexively- the success, contributions, and future potential of SIE towards sustainable energy transitions in Europe. SONNET investigates how, to what extent and under which enabling conditions diverse types of SIE may result in new breakthroughs or successfully help to overcome transition barriers, such as limited citizen engagement or slow adoption of new technologies.

1.2 Objectives of WP6

The aim of WP 6 is to evaluate and assess the success of SIE initiatives to making energy more secure, sustainable, competitive and affordable and to increase competitiveness and preserve livelihoods through their diverse socio-political, socio-cultural and socio-economic contributions (e.g. novel business models, governance arrangements or narratives).

Within this context, the aim of the goal alignment report is to compare European Energy Union objectives to the goals and aims of SIE-initiatives and to identify patterns across different SIE types and countries.

1.3 Definition of key concepts

Throughout this document we will use the following concepts¹ (alphabetical order):

- **Aim:** The directed aim, intent or purpose of the EU Energy Union, the SIE-initiative, SIE-actors, or other field-actors. The words “aim” and “goal” will be used as synonyms in this document.
- **Alignment:** The extent to which different actors and institutions share the same aims, i.e. have a similar strength (“strong” vs. “weak”) of support for the aims.
- **EU-aim:** An aim which is a policy goal of the EU.
- **Field-actors:** are individuals, organizations or other collectives who are part of a certain SIE-field – these can enable or impede social innovation in the energy sector (SIE). They can be from every sphere of society (community, market, state, third sector).

¹ In line with SONNET deliverable D1.2.

- Output: intermediate result of an SIE which contributes indirectly to different aims or objectives, but does not create a direct impact with regards to any of the aims that are investigated.
- SIE: A social innovation in the energy sector (SIE) is a combination of ideas, objects and/or actions that change social relations and involve new ways of doing, thinking and/or organising energy.
- SIE-aim: An aim which is not a EU-aim, and was only found in the literature on SIE-initiatives.
- SIE-field: is an arena/ space that includes a specific SIE as well as SIE-actors working on it and field actors enabling and/or impeding it. In this space these actors take one another and their actions into account and have a shared (but not necessarily consensual) understanding of a SIE and of their relationship to other actors. They recognise (but not necessarily follow) shared norms, beliefs and rules.
- SIE-initiative: a localised version/ manifestation in time and space of an SIE. It includes SIE actors, as those actors working on SIE.
- SIE-members: individuals that belong to an SIE-initiative, regardless of whether they are SIE-representatives or do not have an official role within the SIE-initiative.
- SIE-representatives: individuals, that can speak for an SIE-initiative, such as the founders, president, program manager or spokesperson, or any other SIE-member that has an official role within the SIE-initiative.

2 METHOD

2.1 Data Collection

The data gathering process consisted of three steps. We first composed a list of the aims of the EU as well as different SIE-initiatives in the energy sector based on a review of relevant academic articles and grey literature in SONNET WP1, task T1.1 (cf. Annex 2: Reviewed Literature Sources). As a second step, the results from our literature review were then presented at a SONNET consortium meeting in Rotterdam on 30th January 2020. During this meeting, the initial list of aims was clustered into 20 groups of similar aims. Both the original list of all aims and the resulting shortlist of 20 aims can be found in "Annex 3: Extended List of Aims".

Table 1: Consolidated list of aims.

Aim	Description	Source
consumer bill	reduce energy bill for consumers	Both
energy consumption	reduce energy consumption	Both
energy efficiency	increase energy efficiency	Both
greenhouse gas emissions	reduce greenhouse gas emissions	Both
impact on environment	reduce impact on the environment	SIE
independence of supplies	increase independence of energy supplies	SIE
knowledge transfer	improve the transfer of knowledge in the energy sector	SIE
local community	strengthen local community	SIE
local economic development	increase local economic development	SIE
new renewable technologies	develop new renewable energy technologies	EU
policy processes	impact energy policy processes	SIE
quality of life	improve quality of life	SIE
regional renewable projects	advocate for regional renewable energy projects	SIE
renewables production	increase the production from renewable energy sources	Both
renewables profitability	improve economic feasibility of renewable energy projects	SIE
security of supply	improve security of energy supply	EU
social acceptance	improve social acceptance of renewable energy production	SIE
support energy projects	provide support for other energy-related initiatives or projects	SIE
trade	increase trade of energy with neighbouring regions	EU

To avoid overloading our surveys, the remainder of WP6 only used the shortlist of 20 aims which is also shown in Table 1. The last column indicates whether an aim was only found in the literature on SIE-initiatives ("SIE"), or in the EU documents describing the European Union's goals ("EU"), or in both ("Both"). The EU goals of reduced consumer bills, reduced energy consumption, higher energy efficiency, reduced greenhouse gas emissions and increasing renewables production were also mentioned in the literature on SIE-initiatives, which indicates an alignment between

SIE-initiatives and the EU in these policy areas, which will be further explored in the remainder of the report.

In a third and last step, we elicited the perceived importance of these aims through two different versions of a first online survey conducted in WP6 (to distinguish it from other surveys conducted in WP6, we refer to this survey as "survey 1"). Version 1 of survey 1 was used to elicit the perceived importance of the aims for an *individual SIE-initiative* from *SIE-representatives and SONNET researchers*. Version 2 was used to elicit the perceived importance of these aims for an *SIE-field* from the perspective of a *field-actor*. In both cases, respondents had to rate the importance of each aim on a 4-point Likert-scale (0= Not important, 1=Hardly important, 2=Moderately important, 3=Very important).

The goal alignment analysis in this report is based on the 45 responses by SONNET researchers, 20 responses of SIE-representatives and 36 responses of field-actors that were collected through the two versions of survey 1 until the 28th May 2021. This corresponds to a full coverage of all the SIE-initiatives that were interviewed within SONNET work package 3. Invitations to the surveys were circulated by researchers from SONNET WP3 (and WP2) at the end of the interviews with the SIE field-actors. Both versions of survey 1, as well as the additional surveys that were planned for WP6, and further details regarding the data collection process can be found in "Annex 5: WP6 Methodological Guidelines".

2.2 Data Analysis

For the analysis of goal alignment, we use two main methods:

- *Average importance*: average importance rating for different groups of respondents.

The average importance rating of an aim measures how important this aim was perceived to be by the corresponding group of respondents. For better interpretability, aims are sorted by average importance.

- *Correlations*: pairwise correlations between the average importance rating by different respondent groups.

Correlations between the importance rating of different aims allow us to detect potential alignment (=positive correlation) or potential mis-alignment (=negative correlation) between different aims for each of the aim types. For better interpretability, correlations are sorted.

Unless otherwise stated, importance ratings include the responses of all researchers, SIE-representatives, and field-actors that were provided using survey 1 (version 1 and version 2, respectively). Aims for which no rating was provided were assumed to have a low importance (Likert-scale rating 0="Not important").

3 RESULTS

3.1 Average importance of all aims

As first step of analysis we calculated the average importance of different aims. Ranking these values in ascending or descending order allows us to quantify the importance of different policy goals for SIE-initiatives.

As shown in Figure 1, the most important goals from the perspective of SIE-initiatives are an increased “renewables production” and a reduction of “greenhouse gas emissions”. With regards to these two aims, the aims of SIE initiatives seem to converge with the EU policy goals.

While the EU-goals of “reduced energy consumption” and increasing “energy efficiency” and increased “renewables profitability” received an average score close to 2 (=moderately important), goals of SIE-initiatives related to their local community that were identified in the literature, such as to increase “social acceptance”, “strengthen local community”, and “impact energy policy processes” were clearly seen as more important.

On average the remaining EU-goals of “security of supply”, “consumer bills”, “new renewable technologies”, and in particular “trade” were mostly seen as hardly important or not important, which indicates that SIE-initiatives may be less well aligned with the EU on these goals.

Figure 1: Average importance of aims for SIE-initiatives.

3.2 Average importance of EU-aims per SIE-field

Looking more in detail at the different SIE-fields, in Table 2 we show the average importance of each of the EU-aims for each of the SIE-fields that were defined in WP1 (see deliverable D1.1). For example, on average the respondents who answered the survey for “Cooperative energy production & consumption” assumed that the aim of “renewables production” was “very Important” (=2.8 Points on the Likert-scale) for energy production & consumption cooperatives (cf. top-left corner of Table 2). The columns (=aims) of Table 2 are sorted according to weighted average importance rating across all SIE-fields (weighted by the number of respondents). The rows (=SIE-fields) are sorted according to (arithmetic) average importance rating across all EU-aims. The most important EU-aim(s) for each SIE-field are highlighted in red.

Table 2: Average importance of aims per SIE-field

#n	SIE-field	EU-policy goal										average
		renewables production	greenhouse gas emissions	energy consumption	renewables profitability	energy efficiency	security of supply	consumer bill	new renewable technologies	trade		
30	Cooperative energy production & consumption	2.8	2.4	2.0	2.0	1.6	1.4	1.2	1.1	0.5	4.5	
10	Investment and finance mechanisms	2.3	2.3	2.1	1.9	2.1	1.5	1.8	1.4	1.0	2.6	
8	Local peer-to-peer electricity exchange	2.6	2.5	1.9	2.1	2.0	2.5	2.0	1.8	1.0	2.6	
10	Energy gamification & nudges	2.4	2.2	2.0	1.2	1.8	1.3	1.1	1.0	0.8	2.4	
8	Advocacy for specific energy pathways	2.6	2.5	1.8	1.4	1.6	1.4	1.6	1.0	0.5	2.2	
4	Action against specific energy pathways	2.0	3.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	1.8	2.0	1.3	2.2	
2	Collaborative eco-efficient housing	2.5	3.0	3.0	2.0	1.5	1.5	2.0	1.5	1.5	2.1	
4	For profit services and technologies	2.3	2.3	2.3	1.8	1.5	1.5	1.3	1.8	1.3	2.0	
3	Energy education	2.7	2.7	2.3	1.3	2.3	1.7	1.3	1.3	0.7	1.9	
8	Non-profit consulting	2.4	1.9	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.0	0.6	0.8	0.4	1.9	
5	Peer to peer learning	2.8	1.6	1.6	2.0	1.8	0.8	1.8	1.2	0.4	1.9	
5	Participatory experimentation and incubation	2.2	2.0	1.2	1.4	0.8	1.4	1.4	1.8	0.6	1.8	
1	Campaigns against specific energy pathways	3.0	3.0	2.0	1.0	2.0	1.0	1.0	3.0	0.0	1.7	
1	Local energy production and consumption	3.0	2.0	0.0	3.0	0.0	3.0	0.0	3.0	0.0	1.5	
2	Participatory energy dialogues	3.0	1.5	2.0	2.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	1.3	
	weighted average	2.6	2.3	1.9	1.8	1.7	1.4	1.4	1.3	0.7	2.9	

As we have already seen in the previous section, from the perspective of SIE-initiatives, renewables production (average importance across all respondents and fields = 2.6) and greenhouse gas emissions (average importance across all respondents and fields = 2.3) are the most important EU-aims. For each of the SIE-fields, at least one of these two aims is (among) the most important aim(s).

Some of the other aims, such as a lower energy consumption, increased energy efficiency, security of supply and the development of new renewable technologies achieved an equally high importance rating as “renewables production” and lower “greenhouse gas emissions” by at least one of the SIE-fields. However, it should be noted that for some of the fields – such as “Local energy production and consumption” – the survey was only answered by 1 respondent. The answers for this field, and other fields with few respondents are thus much less certain than the answers for fields such as “Energy gamification & nudges”, which were evaluated by 10 or more respondents.

3.3 Correlations between importance of aims

As a second step, we used pairwise correlations to explore the similarity or alignment of different aims. An overview of the correlation between importance rankings for each pair of aims is shown in Figure 2. The figure only shows correlations, which are significant at least at the p=10% level.

Figure 2: Heatmap of correlations between importance rankings for A) EU-aims, B) EU- and SIE-aims and C) SIE-aims, which are significant at p=10% level

All significant correlations have a positive sign, which indicates an alignment between the different aims. For a more detailed discussion, we have grouped the data in Figure 2 into correlations that indicate (A) the alignment between different EU-aims, (B) the alignment between SIE-aims and EU-aims and (C) the alignment between different SIE-aims. We will discuss the most important positive and negative correlations for each of these groups in separate sections below.

3.3.1 EU-aims

To filter out the most important correlations between importance of EU-aims, in Table 3 we have sorted the correlations from section (A) of Figure 2 in descending order. To focus on the most important correlations, we only show the ten pairs with the highest correlation. A full list of all correlations is shown in Figure 2 above. Next to each aim, we show the average importance score for the aim across all SIE-fields respondents. So for example, the importance ratings of “trade” (average importance=0.7) and “new renewable technologies” (average importance=1.3) were correlated with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.62 (cf. second row of Table 3).

Table 3: Correlation of importance between different EU goals

	correlation of importances	first EU-aim		second EU-aim	
		aim	importance	aim	importance
highest correlations > 0.5	0.81	energy efficiency	1.7	energy consumption	1.9
	0.62	trade	0.7	new renewable technologies	1.3
	0.62	security of supply	1.4	new renewable technologies	1.3
	0.59	renewables profitability	1.8	new renewable technologies	1.3
	0.58	greenhouse gas emission	2.3	energy consumption	1.9
	0.57	trade	0.7	security of supply	1.4
	0.57	security of supply	1.4	consumer bill	1.4
	0.57	greenhouse gas emission	2.3	energy efficiency	1.7
	0.53	security of supply	1.4	greenhouse gas emissions	2.3
	0.52	trade	0.7	consumer bill	1.4
0.52	greenhouse gas emission	2.3	consumer bill	1.4	
0.51	new renewable technolo	1.3	consumer bill	1.4	

The strongest positive correlation was between the importance ratings for higher energy efficiency and lower energy consumption. Intuitively this makes sense because energy efficiency is one of the means to achieve a lower energy consumption. Besides that, it is striking to see that many of the other correlations above 0.5 are between the aim of new renewable technologies and other EU policy goals. One potential interpretation of these findings could be that new renewable technologies were sometimes perceived as a means to achieve these other policy goals.

3.3.2 EU-aims and SIE-aims

In Table 4 we have sorted the correlations from section (B) of Figure 2 in descending order. To focus on the most important correlations, we only show the ten pairs with the highest correlation. Next to each aim, we show the average importance score for the aim.

Table 4: Correlation of importance between EU-aims and SIE-aims

	correlation of importances	SIE-aim		EU-aim	
		aim	importance	aim	importance
highest correlations > 0	0.56	quality of life	1.9	greenhouse gas emissions	2.3
	0.51	regional renewable proje	1.7	renewables profitability	1.8
	0.47	impact on environment	2.3	consumer bill	1.4
	0.47	regional renewable proje	1.7	renewables production	2.6
	0.42	regional renewable proje	1.7	new renewable technologies	1.3
	0.42	policy processes	2.2	energy efficiency	1.7
	0.41	policy processes	2.2	energy consumption	1.9
	0.4	independence of supplie	1.8	energy consumption	1.9
	0.39	local economic developn	2	new renewable technologies	1.3
	0.39	quality of life	1.9	consumer bill	1.4

The strongest positive correlation was between the quality of life and reduced greenhouse gas emissions. This could indicate an assumption by SIE-initiatives that a rising global temperature will have a negative effect on the quality of life. Apart from that there are several high correlations between aims related to renewables, such as new renewable technologies / regional renewable projects / renewables profitability, which may indicate a certain degree of similarity between these aims.

3.3.3 SIE-aims

In Table 5 we have sorted the correlations from section (C) of Figure 2 in descending order. To focus on the most important correlations, we only show the ten pairs with the highest correlation. Next to each aim, we show the average importance score for the aim.

Table 5: Correlation of importance between different SIE-aims

	correlation of importances	first SIE-aim		second SIE-aim	
		aim	importance	aim	importance
highest correlations >0	0.6	regional renewable projects	1.7	local economic development	2
	0.56	local economic development	2	local community	2.3
	0.5	quality of life	1.9	impact on environment	2.3
	0.48	social acceptance	2.3	independence of supplies	1.8
	0.46	support energy projects	1.9	knowledge transfer	2
	0.44	regional renewable projects	1.7	independence of supplies	1.8
	0.44	social acceptance	2.3	knowledge transfer	2
	0.44	local economic development	2	independence of supplies	1.8
	0.42	local community	2.3	independence of supplies	1.8
	0.42	policy processes	2.2	knowledge transfer	2

As we can see in Table 5, there is a high correlation between the importance rating for an increasing independence of supplies and other goals with a strong regional component, such as regional renewable projects, local economic development and a strengthening of the local community. This could indicate important synergies between these aims.

In a similar way, the aim of knowledge transfer was positively correlated with aims such as supporting renewable projects, increasing social acceptance, and impacting policy processes, indicating a positive alignment between these aims.

3.4 Correlation of aim importance rating by different respondent types

Perceived importance, as elicited during our surveys, is a subjective measure. In this section we therefore test to what extent the average importance of an aim for an SIE-initiative depends on the respondent that provides the rating.

For this purpose, Figure 3 shows the scatterplots of the average importance rating for different aims by SIE-representatives vs. researchers (left), SIE-representatives vs. field-actors (center) and researchers vs. field-actors (right) for each of the aims. In the top-left corner of each scatterplot, we have displayed the correlation between the importance ratings.

Figure 3: Average importance rating by participants vs. researchers (left), participants vs. field-actors (center) and researchers vs. field-actors (right) for each aim

The importance ratings which are most strongly correlated are those of participants and field-actors (Figure 3, center). The importance rating of researchers is also strongly correlated with each of these two groups. However, researchers tend to assume a lower importance than field-actors (Figure 3, right) and participants (Figure 3, left), in particular for aims that are seen as unimportant.

Overall, we interpret the strong alignment between the importance ratings of the different respondent types as a sign for a high level of agreement between these groups.

As outlined in the methodology guidelines, in the remainder of the SONNET project we will use a series of different contribution metrics to test whether this agreement about the perceived importance of different aims is also reflected by objectively measurable higher contributions towards those aims which are seen as important.

4 LIMITATIONS

The high correlation between the importance ratings by researchers, SIE-representatives and field-actors is an encouraging sign, and indicates that the perceptions of different actors regarding the importance of different aims for an SIE-initiative are robust across respondents. However, for many of the SIE-initiatives and SIE-fields, the number of respondents that have provided an assessment is very small. To obtain a statistically more robust result would require a larger number of respondents for each SIE-initiative and SIE-field. As part of the subsequent deliverable D6.2 we plan to evaluate the robustness of responses to survey 1, which were analyzed in this deliverable, by comparing them to the importance ratings provided by a larger number of members of the SIE-initiatives who decide to participate in the members survey (Survey 3, cf. Annex 5: WP6 Methodological Guidelines).

In section 3, we have mentioned some of the explanations regarding the high correlations between importance ratings which seem most plausible. However, it should be noted that apart from these reasons, high correlations may also be caused by other factors. Instead of synergies between the aims, or a similarity of the different concepts, correlations could also be due to personality traits and the response strategy of survey respondents. For example, respondents that care about one aim (e.g. security), could simply happen to care more about another aim (e.g. consumer bills), even though these two aims do not create synergies, and may even require a trade-off. To account for this possibility, we therefore talked about “potential explanations”, to indicate that some of the results may also have been driven by other reasons.

Perceived importance of different aims does not provide an indication about an SIE-initiative's contribution to EU-policy goals. In the subsequent deliverable D6.2, we therefore plan to complement our analysis regarding aim importance from this survey, with an analysis of the perceived and the objectively measured contributions of different SIE-initiatives and SIE-fields to EU energy policy goals.

Finally, while we have investigated the average importance of different aims for each country in Annex 4; we believe, however, that the average importance ratings per aim and country may be biased. This can be traced back to the sampling strategy of the SONNET consortium, where researchers investigated different SIE-fields in different countries. We have therefore not discussed the average importance ratings in more detail in this report. Instead, we will separate the statistical contribution of the respondent type, SIE-field and country through a multi-variate regression of aim importance and contributions controlling for these factors in the subsequent deliverable D6.2.

5 CONCLUSIONS

There is a strong support among SIE-initiatives for the EU-aims of increased renewables production and reduced greenhouse gas emissions.

Our analysis confirms that SIE-initiatives attach more weight to the aims that were mentioned by the literature on aims of SIE-initiatives, such as a strengthening of the local community, or having an impact on energy policy processes. However, they also show a moderate support for the EU-goals of reduced energy consumption, increasing energy efficiency and increased renewables profitability, indicating a certain degree of alignment with these EU-goals.

On average, the remaining EU-goals of increasing security of supply, reducing consumer bills, developing new renewable technologies, and in particular increasing trade were seen as hardly important or not important, indicating that the participating SIE-initiatives were not aligned with these EU-goals.

Regarding the correlation between importance ratings for different aims, all of the statistically relevant correlations were positive. One reason for this could be that some of these aims are fairly similar concepts (such as “energy efficiency” and “reduced energy consumption”) or that there are synergies between these aims (such as in case of “regional renewables projects” and “knowledge transfer”). However, positive correlations could also be caused by other reasons, such as a bias by some respondents to attach a higher importance to all aims.

As a next step in the SONNET project, we will analyze to what extent the high importance ratings are also reflected in a higher perceived – and objectively measured - contribution of the SIE-initiatives towards EU energy policy goals.

Annex 1: EC Summary Requirements

Changes with respect to the DoA

The deliverable was submitted as planned. The country comparisons will be considered further in the upcoming deliverable D6.2.

Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable extends the empirical work within WP3 (SIE case studies) and WP2 (SIE in SONNET cities) and complements the qualitative analysis in these work packages with quantitative findings. Results will be discussed with SONNET's city partners and will be used in SONNET's dissemination activities.

Short Summary of results

Based on a survey with SIE-representatives, field-actors and researchers, we have evaluated to what extent the aims of SIE-initiatives are aligned with the goals of EU energy policy. We find that there is a strong support among SIE-initiatives for the EU-aims of increased renewables production and reduced greenhouse gas emissions. The other EU-aims which we tested were perceived by our survey respondents as less important than the SIE-initiatives own aims. Regarding the correlation between importance ratings for different aims, most aims were positively correlated. One reason for this could be that some of these aims are fairly similar concepts (such as "energy efficiency" and "reduced energy consumption") or that there are synergies between these aims (such as in case of "regional renewables projects" and "knowledge transfer").

Evidence of accomplishment

This document and underlying data. In line with our data management plan, anonymized survey results and scripts will be made available on Zenodo after completion of WP6 analysis to the extent consent procedures allow to do so.

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Annex 3: Extended List of Aims

Aim	Sub-categories before SONNET consortium meeting in Rotterdam
consumer bill	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> improve economic access/affordability to energy (e.g. reduce fuel poverty)
energy consumption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> reduce energy consumption trigger change in energy consumption behavior
energy efficiency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> increase energy efficiency address energy poverty through energy efficiency
greenhouse gas emissions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> reduce GHG Emissions
impact on environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> protect the local or regional natural environment improve/sustain local or regional (cultural) landscape quality
independence of supplies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> strengthen local self-sufficiency / autarky reduce dependency from dominant market players and/or countries (e.g. large energy suppliers, oil-producing countries) balance power relations
knowledge transfer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> improve energy literacy (raise awareness, education on energy issues)
local community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> strengthen sense of community improve social inclusion (gender, age, ethnicity) improve social capital (social interactions, social cohesion, trust) improve/sustain local or regional (cultural) landscape quality
local economic development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> contribute to economic decentralization of energy system generate a profit increase jobs locally promote local or regional (economic) development promote regionality of production, consumption and trade
new renewable technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> promote R&D projects in energy develop new technological solutions
policy processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> contribute to a more "just" energy system advocate for more ambitious/reliable energy policy improve the democratic quality of the energy transition
quality of life	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> improve/sustain well-being/quality of life
regional renewable projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> engage in (political) interest representation (e.g. network of small initiatives, intermediary function) prevent realization of close-by infrastructure (e.g. wind power, nuclear disposal) advocate to phase-out non-renewable energy (e.g. nuclear, coal)
renewables production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> increase the production from RES
renewables profitability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> finance RE investment through local ownership facilitate equal access to use and/or ownership of renewable energy facilities provide attractive investment opportunities create new market structures (e.g. exchange of certificates of origin) improve economic viability of RES
security of supply	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> improve grid resilience/stability reduce the risk of blackouts/shortages to energy supplies invest in the grid (includes digitalization and smartness)
social acceptance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> improve social acceptance of renewable energies
support energy projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> provide resources (financial, consulting, etc.) for other initiatives create networks to foster knowledge transfer improve skills and expertise (management of RET, human capital, engagement)
trade	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> increase trade with neighbouring regions and countries

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Annex 4: Average importance per country

Country	Field	Average aim Importance																		
		consumer bill	energy consumption	energy efficiency	greenhouse gas emissions	impact on environment	independence of supplies	knowledge transfer	local community	local economic development	new renewable technology	policy processes	quality of life	regional renewable projects	renewables production	renewables profitability	security of supply	social acceptance	support energy projects	trade
Belgium	Advocacy for specific energy pathways	2.00	1.00	1.00	3.00	3.00	1.00	0.00	2.00	1.00	0.00	1.00	2.00	1.00	3.00	2.00	1.00	0.00	2.00	0.00
Belgium	Participatory experimentation and incubation	3.00	2.00	1.00	2.00	2.00	0.00	2.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	2.00	2.00	0.00	2.00	0.00	2.00	1.00	2.00
Belgium	Total	2.50	1.50	1.00	2.50	2.50	0.50	1.00	1.50	1.00	0.00	1.50	2.00	0.50	2.50	1.00	1.50	0.50	2.00	0.00
France	Cooperative energy production & consumption	0.00	1.67	1.33	1.00	1.67	1.00	0.00	1.67	1.33	0.00	1.00	0.00	1.33	3.00	1.33	0.33	1.67	1.00	0.00
France	Energy gamification & nudges	1.50	1.75	1.25	2.25	2.25	1.75	2.50	3.00	2.50	0.75	2.00	2.25	2.00	2.75	1.75	1.75	3.00	1.50	1.00
France	For profit services and technologies	1.00	2.50	1.50	2.50	2.50	1.50	3.00	2.50	1.50	1.50	3.00	2.50	1.00	2.50	1.50	1.50	3.00	2.50	1.00
France	Non-profit consulting	0.00	1.33	1.00	0.33	0.33	0.00	1.67	1.67	2.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	2.00	2.67	0.67	0.00	1.33	2.33	0.00
France	Participatory energy dialogues	0.00	3.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	3.00	2.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	2.00	3.00	2.00	0.00	3.00	3.00	0.00
France	Total	0.50	2.05	1.42	1.62	1.75	1.25	1.83	2.37	1.87	0.45	1.60	0.95	1.67	2.78	1.45	0.72	2.40	2.07	0.40
Germany	Advocacy for specific energy pathways	1.33	1.33	1.33	2.00	1.67	2.33	1.67	3.00	2.67	1.33	2.67	2.67	2.67	3.00	1.33	1.67	2.67	2.00	1.33
Germany	Collaborative eco-efficient housing	1.00	3.00	0.00	3.00	3.00	0.00	3.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	3.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	1.00	1.00	3.00	3.00	0.00
Germany	Cooperative energy production & consumption	1.50	2.50	2.00	2.50	2.50	2.00	1.00	2.50	1.00	0.00	0.50	2.50	0.50	2.50	1.00	0.50	1.50	1.00	0.00
Germany	Energy education	1.33	2.33	2.33	2.67	2.67	1.67	2.67	2.00	2.00	1.33	3.00	1.67	1.00	2.67	1.33	1.67	2.33	2.00	0.67
Germany	Investment and finance mechanisms	2.00	2.50	2.00	2.50	2.50	1.50	3.00	2.50	2.50	1.50	3.00	2.50	2.00	1.50	2.50	1.00	3.00	1.50	1.50
Germany	Participatory energy dialogues	0.00	1.00	0.00	1.00	2.00	3.00	1.00	2.00	2.00	0.00	3.00	1.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	0.00	3.00	3.00	2.00
Germany	Participatory experimentation and incubation	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	3.00	0.00	0.00	2.00	2.00	0.00	0.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	0.00	0.00
Germany	Total	1.02	1.81	1.10	1.95	2.05	1.50	2.19	1.86	1.45	0.88	2.45	1.76	1.60	2.38	1.60	1.12	2.50	1.79	0.79
Poland	Advocacy for specific energy pathways	3.00	2.00	2.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	2.00	3.00	2.00	2.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	0.00
Poland	Campaigns against specific energy pathways	1.00	2.00	2.00	3.00	2.00	1.00	3.00	0.00	0.00	3.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	3.00	1.00	1.00	3.00	1.00	0.00
Poland	For profit services and technologies	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	3.00	1.00	1.00	3.00	2.00	1.00	2.00	3.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Poland	Local peer-to-peer electricity exchange	3.00	2.00	1.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	3.00	1.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	1.00
Poland	Non-profit consulting	3.00	2.00	2.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	1.00	1.00	3.00	3.00	1.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	1.00
Poland	Participatory experimentation and incubation	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	2.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	2.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	3.00
Poland	Total	2.33	2.00	1.83	2.67	2.83	2.17	2.17	2.17	1.83	2.17	2.33	2.67	1.67	2.50	2.17	2.17	2.50	1.83	1.00
Switzerland	Collaborative eco-efficient housing	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	3.00	1.00	3.00
Switzerland	Cooperative energy production & consumption	1.00	2.00	1.50	3.00	2.50	3.00	2.50	2.50	2.50	1.00	2.50	1.50	2.00	3.00	3.00	1.00	2.50	3.00	0.00
Switzerland	Energy gamification & nudges	0.00	2.50	2.50	2.50	1.50	2.00	2.00	1.50	1.50	0.50	3.00	2.00	0.00	2.50	0.50	0.50	1.50	1.50	0.00
Switzerland	For profit services and technologies	2.00	3.00	2.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	2.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	2.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	3.00	3.00	2.00
Switzerland	Investment and finance mechanisms	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	0.00	3.00	0.00	3.00	3.00	1.00	0.00	3.00	3.00	0.00
Switzerland	Peer to peer learning	2.25	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	1.75	2.00	2.75	2.50	1.50	2.75	1.50	3.00	2.75	1.75	1.00	2.25	2.00	0.50
Switzerland	Total	1.38	2.08	1.83	2.25	2.00	2.46	2.42	2.46	2.42	1.50	2.88	1.67	2.00	2.88	2.04	1.08	2.54	2.25	0.92
The Netherlands	Advocacy for specific energy pathways	1.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	2.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	1.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	3.00	1.00	1.00	3.00	3.00	0.00
The Netherlands	Cooperative energy production & consumption	2.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	3.00	2.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	2.00	3.00	2.00	1.00
The Netherlands	Non-profit consulting	0.50	1.50	2.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	3.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	3.00	2.50	1.50	3.00	1.50	1.00	3.00	2.00	0.50
The Netherlands	Peer to peer learning	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	2.00	3.00	3.00	0.00	2.00	0.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	0.00	1.00	3.00	0.00
The Netherlands	Total	0.88	1.88	2.25	2.25	2.25	1.75	2.50	2.75	2.25	1.50	2.75	2.13	2.38	3.00	1.88	1.00	2.50	2.50	0.38
United Kingdom	Action against specific energy pathways	1.50	1.50	1.50	3.00	3.00	1.00	2.50	2.50	1.50	1.50	3.00	2.50	1.50	1.50	1.50	1.50	1.50	1.50	1.00
United Kingdom	Advocacy for specific energy pathways	1.50	2.00	1.50	2.50	2.50	1.50	3.00	3.00	1.50	0.50	3.00	3.00	1.50	2.00	1.00	1.00	2.50	2.50	0.00
United Kingdom	Cooperative energy production & consumption	0.00	1.00	0.50	1.50	1.00	1.00	1.50	1.50	0.00	0.50	3.00	1.50	0.00	1.00	0.50	0.00	1.50	0.50	0.00
United Kingdom	Investment and finance mechanisms	2.50	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	0.50	1.50	2.50	1.00	0.50	2.00	3.00	0.00	1.50	1.00	1.50	1.50	1.50	0.00
United Kingdom	Non-profit consulting	0.50	1.00	1.00	2.50	3.00	1.00	2.50	1.50	1.50	0.50	1.50	3.00	1.00	1.00	1.50	1.50	2.50	2.50	0.50
United Kingdom	Total	1.20	1.70	1.50	2.50	2.50	1.00	2.20	2.20	1.10	0.70	2.50	2.60	0.80	1.40	1.10	1.10	1.90	2.00	0.30

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Annex 5: WP6 Methodological Guidelines

SONNET – SOCIAL INNOVATION IN ENERGY TRANSITIONS

*Co-creating a rich understanding of the diversity, processes,
contributions, success and future potentials of
social innovation in the energy sector*

WP6 Methodological Guidelines: Evaluation Scheme

Project Coordinator: Fraunhofer ISI

Work Package: 6

Leader Organization: ZHAW (Regina Betz)

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Table of contents

1	EMPIRICAL FOCUS OF WP 6 AND KEY CONCEPTS	27
1.1	Objectives of WP6.....	27
1.2	Definition of key concepts	27
1.3	Main links with other work packages	28
2	PRACTICALITIES	29
2.1	Partner roles.....	29
2.2	Budget.....	31
2.3	Timeline	31
2.4	Contact point	31
3	DATA GATHERING PROCESS.....	32
4	DATA GATHERING INSTRUMENTS.....	34
4.1	Survey 1: Aims and Contributions	36
4.1.1	Survey 1 Version 1: Researchers and SIE-representatives.....	25
4.1.2	Survey 1 Version 2: Field-actors	41
4.2	Survey 2: SMART indicators and output measures.....	45
4.3	Survey 3: SIE-participant views	54
	EVALUATION METHODS	63
4.4	Averages and Rankings	63
4.5	Pairwise correlations.....	65
4.6	Multi-variate regressions	68
5	WORK PLAN AND KEY DATES	69

1 EMPIRICAL FOCUS OF WP 6 AND KEY CONCEPTS

1.1 Objectives of WP6

The main objectives of WP 6 are:

1. To map the alignment between the aims of the EU Energy Union and the aims of different SIE-initiatives (T6.1)
2. To develop (T6.2) and apply (T6.3) an evaluation scheme of SMART indicators and additional benefits for better understanding successful examples of SIE-initiatives and their related contributions to the aims of the European Energy Union.

1.2 Definition of key concepts

Throughout this document we will use the following concepts (alphabetical order):

- **Aim:** The directed aim, intent or purpose of the EU Energy Union, the SIE-initiative, SIE-actors, or other Field-actors. The words “aim” and “goal” will be used as synonyms in this document.
- **Alignment:** The extent, to which different actors and institutions share the same aims. This includes both the direction (“support for” vs. “opposition to” a specific outcome) and the strength (“strong” vs. “weak” support) of different aims for each of the actors.
- **Contributions:** Contributions of SIE-initiatives are the intended and unintended effects of SIE-initiatives in relation to energy systems.
- **Field-actors:** are individuals, organizations or other collectives who are part of a certain SIE-field – these can enable or impede SIE. They can be from every sphere of society (community, market, state, third sector).
- **Impact:** final result of an SIE which directly contributes to an aim or objective.
- **Output:** intermediate result of an SIE which contributes indirectly to different aims or objectives, but does not create a direct impact with regards to any of the aims that are investigated.
- **SIE:** A Social innovation in the energy sector (SIE) is a combination of ideas, objects and/or actions that change social relations and involve new ways of doing, thinking and/or organising energy.
- **SIE-actors:** are individuals, organizations or other collectives who are part of a certain SIE-field and actively work on SIE. They can be from every sphere of society (community, market, state, third sector).
- **SIE-field:** is an arena/space that includes a specific SIE as well as SIE-actors working on it and field actors enabling and/or impeding it. In this space these actors take one another and their actions into account and have a shared (but not necessarily consensual) understanding of a SIE and of their relationship to other actors. They recognise (but not necessarily follow) shared norms, beliefs and rules.
- **SIE-initiative:** a localised version/manifestation in time and space of an SIE. It includes SIE actors, as those actors working on SIE.
- **SIE-members:** individuals that belong to an SIE-initiative, regardless of whether they are SIE-representatives or do not have an official role within the SIE-initiative.
- **SIE-representatives:** individuals, that can speak for an SIE-initiative, such as the founders, president, program manager or spokesperson, or any other SIE-member that has an official role within the SIE-initiative.
- **Success:** Success of SIE is the extent to which SIE-initiatives meet their aims and/or otherwise formulated system aims, such as EU policy objectives.

1.3 Main links with other work packages

The research for WP6 will be closely integrated with the other work packages through the following main linkages:

- WP3: In-depth interviews with Field-actors and SIE-actors will be used to collect information regarding the perceived importance, contribution and success measurement approaches of different SIE initiatives and prepare the follow-up assessment by WP6 Analysts.
- WP5: Citizen surveys may complement the assessment of historical success and contributions in WP6 by investigating the potential future contribution of SIE-Initiatives, e.g. by assessing the interest of the wider population to support the (aims of) SIE-initiatives and / or the EU.
- WP2: The WP6 questionnaires will be sent after the interviews with interview partners in WP2. They will be used to collect information regarding the perceived importance, contribution and success measurement approaches of different SIE initiatives those network actors are aware of and will complement the information gained from WP3.

A close cooperation between these work-packages will thus be needed to achieve a holistic, multi-level assessment of the success of different SIE-initiatives.

2 PRACTICALITIES

2.1 Partner roles

WP6 Analysts:

- Develop the evaluation scheme for goal-alignment and measurement of success
- Evaluate responses to Survey 1-3
- Write-up results in D6.1 (EU and SIE goal alignment map) M25 and D6.3 (SIE evaluation: Characterizing successful SIE to enable secure, sustainable, competitive, and affordable energy transitions)

WP6 Reviewers:

- Review the WP6 deliverables D6.1 and D6.3

WP2 Researchers:

- Send WP6 Survey 1,2 after the WP2 interviews (cf. section 3) and send reminders, if necessary

WP3 Coordinators:

- Review the “WP6 methodological guidelines - implications for WP3” (this document)
- Review translation of WP6 Surveys to local language (Polish, Dutch, French)
- Forward the WP6 methodological guidelines (this document) and coordinate the collection of WP6 Survey 1 by WP3 researches

WP3 Researchers:

- Include WP6 Survey 1 in the WP3 interviews (cf. section 3)
- Invite SIE-actors and Field-actors to participate in follow-up by WP6 Analysts

City Partners:

- Provide SMART indicators for their city, their country (as a benchmark) as well as SIE-initiatives within their city (cf. section 4.2 below)

An overview of the partners and their roles at the time of writing is given in Table 1 below.

An up-to-date overview of all partners, roles and addresses can be found on the SONNET cloud: [SONNET cloud\08_WP8 management\01_T8_1 internal coms\01_Team](#)

Table 6: Persons involved in WP6.

COUNTRY	PARTNER	INDIVIDUAL	ROLE(S)
CH	ZHAW	Regina Betz	WP6 Lead
			WP6 Analyst
			WP2 Researcher
	ZHAW	Lukas Braunreiter	WP2 Researcher
	ZHAW	Tim Dzukowski	WP6 Analyst
	ZHAW	Leticia Müller	WP3 Researcher
	ZHAW	Jörg Musiolik	WP3 Coordinator
FR	GEM	Anne-Lorene Vernay	Goal Analysis
			WP6 Analyst
			WP3 Coordinator
	GEM	Adelie Ranville	WP2 Researcher
			WP3 Researcher
			WP2 Researcher
DE	ISI	Karoline Rogge	WP3 Coordinator
			WP2 Lead
	ISI	Maria Stadler	WP3 Researcher
			WP2 Researcher
			WP2 Researcher
NL	DRIFT	Julia Wittmayer	WP3 Researcher
			WP2 Researcher
	DRIFT	Maria Fraaije	WP3 Researcher
			WP2 Researcher
PL	KOZ	Agata Dembek	WP3 Researcher
			WP3 Researcher
	KOZ	Marta Struminska	WP3 Researcher
			WP2 Researcher
UK	UoS	Sabine Hielscher	WP2 Researcher
			WP3 Coordinator
	UoS	Marfuga Iskandarova	WP2 Researcher
			WP3 Researcher

2.2 Budget

WP3: Depending on the level of experience, we expect that the steps described in section 3 will take about 2-3 working days for WP3 researchers in each country (30 to 60 minutes per interview, for 8 interviews per country; and 1-2d for the review). The remaining time can be used for the review and discussions regarding the refinement of the research method (cf. section 5)

WP3: Research partners from Poland, Netherlands and France will require 1-2 additional days for reviewing translation of the WP6 questions into their local language and translating back the answers to open questions.

City partners: Depending on the amount and the quality of data that is already available, city partners may require up to 5 working days to collect, clean and reformat data regarding the SMART indicators listed in section 4.2 for the SIE-initiatives in their city.

2.3 Timeline

Data gathering for T6.1 (Goal Alignment) and T1.2 starts August 2019 and finishes on 31st March 2021. A detailed timeline can be found under section 6.

2.4 Contact point

If you have any questions or issues, please contact Regina Betz, Christian Winzer and Tim Dzukowski.

3 DATA GATHERING PROCESS

The following list outlines the data gathering approach of WP 6. The time required from WP3 researchers for WP6 work is highlighted in yellow. Annex 1 shows the working process description provided to WP3 researchers.

Table 7: Data gathering process for WP6.

When?	Who?	What task?	Remarks	Time for WP6
Before WP3 interviews	WP3 Researchers	Survey 1 (Aims and Contributions)	Prior to conducting the first interview with every SIE-initiative investigated, researchers from WP3 should complete Survey 1 (see below 4.1.) for the corresponding SIE-initiatives which they plan to interview. Their assessments of aims and contributions will be based on the information gathered during the document review for WP3 (cf. WP3 Mini-Method Guidelines, Section 1.3), or during the interview preparation (cf. WP3.1 “Methodological guidelines”, Section 6.1.2 d).	8-10 mins Per SIE-I
During WP3 interviews	WP3 Researchers	Ask open questions about “Aims goals and Aspirations”	As specified in the “Topic and Observation Guide” for WP3 (D3.1: “Methodological guidelines”, Annex 2), WP3 researchers should ask SIE-representatives about the “Aims? Have these changed over time?” of the SIE-initiative. To avoid anchoring bias, they should do so, before asking them to complete Survey 1.	None (Part of WP3)
End of WP3 interviews	SIE-representatives and Field-actors	Survey 1 (Aims and Contributions)	SIE-representatives and Field-actors should also complete Survey 1. This will allow WP6 Analysts to compare the independent assessments by WP3 researchers, SIE-representatives and Field-actors.	8-15 mins Per interview

When?	Who?	What task?	Remarks	Time for WP6
	WP3 researchers	Announce Follow-up by WP6 and	WP3 researchers should encourage SIE-representatives to take part in the follow-up assessments by WP6 Analysts (see below)	2 mins Per interview
End of WP2 interviews	Interview partners in Cities	Survey 1 (Aims and Contributions)	Interview partners in cities are asked if they volunteer to complete Survey 1 (1a for SIE Representatives; 1b for others). This will provide additional information for WP6 analysis.	2 mins Per interview
Follow-up	SIE-representatives	Survey 2 (SMART Indicators)	For SIE-initiatives who are not located in SONNET cities, WP6 Analysts will ask the contact person specified in Survey 1, question 5, to provide data on the SMART indicators for their SIE-initiative.	0.5 - 1 day per SIE-Initiative
	SIE-members	Survey 3 (SIE-members)	WP6 Analysts will ask the SIE-representative specified in Survey 1 (question 5) to circulate Survey 3 to (some of) their membership base.	8-15 mins per respondent

4 DATA GATHERING INSTRUMENTS

Quantifying the aims and contributions of small actors such as SIE-initiatives is a difficult task because:

- Aims of SIE-initiatives are subjective and heterogeneous
- Contributions and success of SIE-initiatives are hard to quantify, as some of their aims relate to ways of “thinking”, which cannot be inferred from objective actions (i.e. raising awareness and increasing acceptance)
- Data is scarce, as many SIE-initiatives will not have the time that is required to quantify their contributions to all EU-policy objectives

To overcome these problems, we propose to use the surveys in the table below.

Table 8: Overview of surveys used in WP6.

When?	Who?	What instrument?	Type of metric	Unit of analysis	Aims	Contributions
Before WP3 interviews	Researcher	Survey 1 version 1	subjective	SIE-initiative	X	X
End of WP3 or WP2 interviews	SIE-representatives	(Aims and Contributions)	subjective	SIE-initiative	X	X
End of WP3 or WP2 interviews	Field-actors	Survey 1 version 2 (Aims and Contributions)	subjective	SIE-Field	X	X
Follow-up by WP6	SIE-representatives	Survey 2 (SMART indicators)	objective	SIE-initiative		X
Follow-up by WP6	SIE-members	Survey 3 (SIE-member views)	subjective	SIE-member	X	X

This approach has the following advantages:

- Survey 1: Reveals the alignment between aims and contributions of SIE-initiatives an EU policy and allows us to test the accuracy of researcher assessments based on desk research
- Survey 1, version 2: Helps us detect effects, that become salient at the level of SIE-fields, and not individual SIE-initiatives
- Survey 2: Allow us to benchmark the subjective assessments of contributions in Survey 1 against objective (SMART) indicators, at least for some of the main EU-objectives
- Survey 3: Reveals impacts of SIE-initiatives on its members that cannot be captured by SMART indicators
- All Surveys: will allow us to assess the heterogeneity of aims within SIE-initiative and explore biases of the subjective ratings depending on the type of respondent, who carries out the assessment

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WP3 researchers may use the following reasons to encourage SIE-initiatives to participate in the follow-up assessments:

Advantages of participating in follow-up assessment:

Survey 2: SMART indicators:

4.1 Survey 1: Aims and Contributions

Survey 1 contains two main standardized questions on the perceived importance of and contribution to a list of 20 aims from socio-economic, socio-political, socio-cultural, socio-environmental and socio-technical or cross-cutting areas that are potentially relevant to SIE-initiatives. The list of aims was derived from literature on SIE-initiatives, the Energy Union objectives as well as formulated goals of SIE-initiatives in the mapping in WP 1 and includes the feedback from SONNET researchers during the Rotterdam Workshop. If WP3 researchers or SIE-actors feel that important goals are missing, they can specify these at the end of respective questions in Survey 1. Depending on the feedback which WP3 researchers provide through Survey 1 itself as well as during the Warsaw meeting, the list of aims was amended.

Data collection process:

WP6 Analysts email WP3 and WP2 researchers an Excel version of Survey 1. WP3 researchers should fill in the survey themselves (prior to WP3 interviews). WP2 and WP3 researchers should ask their interview partners to fill a copy of survey 1 version 1 or 2 (at the end of WP3 interviews).

4.1.1 Survey 1 Version 1: Researchers and SIE-representatives

Language: English Change the language

Aims and Contributions of energy-related initiatives/ projects

Thank you for starting the survey. In the SONNET research project, we study the aims and contributions of various energy-related initiatives/ projects throughout Europe. We are interested particularly in the intended and unintended aims of these initiatives/ projects on both individuals and the larger energy system and society, as well as how the achievement of an aim is measured.

The research is conducted as part of the Horizon 2020 call: 'Building a low carbon, climate resilient future: secure, clean and efficient energy' call and thus funded by the EU Horizon 2020 programme. For more information about the wider project please visit the SONNET website: <https://sonnet-energy.eu/>.

We would appreciate if you would take 10 minutes to answer the following questions about the initiative you are engaged in within the next week so we can use your responses in our work.

The questions are not sensitive in nature, but ask about your perspectives on the energy-related initiatives/ projects that you are familiar with.

Some questions may be challenging to precisely answer. Just give us your best guess. There are no right or wrong answers.

Your answers will be treated confidentially and will only be accessed by researchers of the SONNET project.

We hope that the results will contribute to open and informed debate on the subject of social innovation in energy transitions.

If you have any questions or concerns, please contact Sabine Hielscher (s.hielscher@sussex.ac.uk) or Christian Winzer (winc@zhaw.ch).

Thank you for your support.

As part of this research project, we need your consent to collect data on your Organization/ project.

The personal data related to this survey includes your name, affiliated initiative/ project, and your email address. Personal data is used only for the survey invitation and tracking of survey completion. Any data that is provided by you is used as research data and will remain strictly confidential, will not be shared with third parties, nor transferred outside of the SONNET project team, and will be stored on institutional servers and retained for 10 years after completing the project.

The research data is not stored with personal data, thus responses are not connected to individuals, and will be analyzed and presented in an anonymized way that does not allow someone to trace the responses back to an individual.

We would like to reassure you that as a participant in this project you have very definite rights: your participation is entirely voluntary and you are free to withdraw your provided information at any time without giving a reason.

Do you consent to the collection, storage and use of the data you provide in the survey as described above?

Yes I consent.

Next

***On behalf of which energy-related initiative/ project do you answer the survey?**

***In which role do you answer the survey?**

Choose one of the following answers

- SONNET Researcher
- Representative of

***Please provide your last name to help us know who has completed the survey.**

Previous

Next

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***From your perspective, how important are the following aims to ORGANISATION-NAME?**

	Very important	Moderately important	Hardly important	Not important	I don't know
improve quality of life	<input type="radio"/>				
impact energy policy processes	<input type="radio"/>				
increase independence of energy supplies	<input type="radio"/>				
reduce energy consumption	<input type="radio"/>				
reduce greenhouse gas emissions	<input type="radio"/>				
increase the production from renewable energy sources	<input type="radio"/>				
reduce impact on the environment	<input type="radio"/>				
improve the transfer of knowledge in the energy sector.	<input type="radio"/>				
improve social acceptance of renewable energy production	<input type="radio"/>				
increase local economic development	<input type="radio"/>				
improve economic feasibility of renewable energy projects	<input type="radio"/>				
provide support for other energy-related initiatives or projects	<input type="radio"/>				
improve security of energy supply	<input type="radio"/>				
develop new renewable energy technologies	<input type="radio"/>				
advocate for regional renewable energy projects	<input type="radio"/>				
increase energy efficiency	<input type="radio"/>				
strengthen local community	<input type="radio"/>				
reduce energy bill for consumers	<input type="radio"/>				
increase trade of energy with neighbouring regions	<input type="radio"/>				

Are there any additional aims which are very important to ORGANISATION-NAME but were not included in the above list? Please list (max. 5) here:

1)

***Do you monitor the achievement of any of the previously mentioned aims in ORGANISATION-NAME?**

- yes
- no
- I don't know

Previous

Next

***When you think about the energy system or society in general, how would you assess the effect ORGANISATION-NAME has had so far in the following areas?**

	Significant effect	Moderate effect	Little effect	No effect	I don't know
an improved quality of life	<input type="radio"/>				
energy policy processes	<input type="radio"/>				
the increased independence of energy supplies	<input type="radio"/>				
the reduction of energy consumption	<input type="radio"/>				
the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions	<input type="radio"/>				
the increase of production from renewable energy sources	<input type="radio"/>				
the reduction of impact on the environment	<input type="radio"/>				
improved knowledge on the energy sector	<input type="radio"/>				
social acceptance of renewable energy production	<input type="radio"/>				
the increase of local economic development	<input type="radio"/>				
the economic feasibility of renewable energy projects	<input type="radio"/>				
the availability of support for other energy-related initiatives or projects	<input type="radio"/>				
improved security of energy supply	<input type="radio"/>				
the development of new renewable energy technologies	<input type="radio"/>				
advocacy for regional renewable energy projects	<input type="radio"/>				
the increase of energy efficiency	<input type="radio"/>				
the strength of local community	<input type="radio"/>				
the reduction of energy bill for consumers	<input type="radio"/>				
the increase of trade of energy with neighbouring regions	<input type="radio"/>				

Previous

Next

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***We are interested in further information on the aims and contributions of ORGANISATION-NAME.**

We would like to know more about the data collected to measure achievement of the aims of ORGANISATION-NAME. Considering this might require some time to look up, we have made a separate online survey for these questions.

Would you be able to answer such questions, if not, could you provide us with a contact person from ORGANISATION-NAME?

Choose one of the following answers

- I am the contact person
- Other contact person
- We do not collect any data and/or are not able to disclose data

***We would also like to ask the individuals engaged in ORGANISATION-NAME (e.g. members, participants, collaborators, stakeholders, etc.) about:**

- what motivates them to participate in ORGANISATION-NAME
- what impact ORGANISATION-NAME has had on them

Who is the best person to contact these individuals with a separate online survey?

Choose one of the following answers

- I am the contact person
- Other contact person
- We do not wish to participate

Previous

Next

Do you have any additional comments, questions, or concerns you would like to share?

Previous

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4.1.2 Survey 1 Version 2: Field-actors

Language: English

Aims and Contributions of energy-related initiatives

Thank you for starting the survey. In the SONNET research project, we study the aims and contributions of various energy-related initiatives/ projects throughout Europe. We are interested particularly in the intended and unintended aims of these initiatives/ projects on both individuals and the larger energy system and society, as well as how the achievement of an aim is measured.

The research is conducted as part of the Horizon 2020 call: 'Building a low carbon, climate resilient future: secure, clean and efficient energy' call and thus funded by the EU Horizon 2020 programme. For more information about the wider project please visit the SONNET website: <https://sonnet-energy.eu/>.

We would appreciate if you would take 10 minutes to answer the following questions about the initiative you are engaged in within the next week so we can use your responses in our work. The questions are not sensitive in nature, but ask about your perspectives on the energy-related initiatives/ projects that you are familiar with.

Some questions may be challenging to precisely answer. Just give us your best guess. There are no right or wrong answers.

Your answers will be treated confidentially and will only be accessed by researchers of the SONNET project.

We hope that the results will contribute to open and informed debate on the subject of social innovation in energy transitions.

If you have any questions or concerns, please contact Sabine Hielscher (s.hielscher@sussex.ac.uk) or Christian Winzer (winc@zhaw.ch).

Thank you for your support.

As part of this research project, we need your consent to collect data on your Organization/ project.

The personal data related to this survey includes your name, affiliated initiative/ project, and your email address. Personal data is used only for the survey invitation and tracking of survey completion. Any data that is provided by you is used as research data and will remain strictly confidential, will not be shared with third parties, nor transferred outside of the SONNET project team, and will be stored on institutional servers and retained for 10 years after completing the project.

The research data is not stored with personal data, thus responses are not connected to individuals, and will be analyzed and presented in an anonymized way that does not allow someone to trace the responses back to an individual.

We would like to reassure you that as a participant in this project you have very definite rights: your participation is entirely voluntary and you are free to withdraw your provided information at any time without giving a reason.

Do you consent to the collection, storage and use of the data you provide in the survey as described above?

Yes I consent.

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***Please indicate the subject area on which you were interviewed by the SONNET researchers to help us classify your answers more easily**

(this should be stated in the E-mail in which the link to this survey was provided)

- Cooperative organisational models for renewable energy
- City-level competitions for sustainable energy
- Participatory incubation and experimentation
- Investment and finance mechanisms
- Framings against specific energy pathways (with a focus on fossil fuel)
- Local electricity exchange

 If you are not sure which answer to select, please contact the person who send you the invitation for this survey.

***Please provide your last name to help us know who has completed the survey.**

Previous

Next

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***When you think about initiatives/ projects within “Cooperative organisational models for renewable energy” in your country, how important do you think are the following aims to these initiatives/ projects?**

	Very important	Moderately important	Hardly important	Not important	I don't know
improve quality of life	<input type="radio"/>				
impact energy policy processes	<input type="radio"/>				
increase independence of energy supplies	<input type="radio"/>				
reduce energy consumption	<input type="radio"/>				
reduce greenhouse gas emissions	<input type="radio"/>				
increase the production from renewable energy sources	<input type="radio"/>				
reduce impact on the environment	<input type="radio"/>				
improve the transfer of knowledge in the energy sector.	<input type="radio"/>				
improve social acceptance of renewable energy production	<input type="radio"/>				
increase local economic development	<input type="radio"/>				
improve economic feasibility of renewable energy projects	<input type="radio"/>				
provide support for other energy-related initiatives or projects	<input type="radio"/>				
improve security of energy supply	<input type="radio"/>				
develop new renewable energy technologies	<input type="radio"/>				
advocate for regional renewable energy projects	<input type="radio"/>				
increase energy efficiency	<input type="radio"/>				
strengthen local community	<input type="radio"/>				
reduce energy bill for consumers	<input type="radio"/>				
increase trade of energy with neighbouring regions	<input type="radio"/>				

Previous

Next

***How would you assess the effect these initiatives/ projects within “Cooperative organisational models for renewable energy” have had all together in the following areas, considering the energy system or society in general?**

Example answer: *So far, these initiatives / projects have had a ... effect on ...*

	Significant effect	Moderate effect	Little effect	No effect	I don't know
an improved quality of life	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
energy policy processes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
the increased independence of energy supplies	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
the reduction of energy consumption	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
the increase of production from renewable energy sources	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
the reduction of impact on the environment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
improved knowledge on the energy sector	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
social acceptance of renewable energy production	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
the increase of local economic development	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
the economic feasibility of renewable energy projects	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
the availability of support for other energy-related initiatives or projects	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
improved security of energy supply	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
the development of new renewable energy technologies	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
advocacy for regional renewable energy projects	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
the increase of energy efficiency	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
the strength of local community	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
the reduction of energy bill for consumers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
the increase of trade of energy with neighbouring regions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>

Previous

Next

Please name up to 10 energy-related initiatives/projects within the field of “Cooperative organisational models for renewable energy” which seem most effective and/or well known to you.

1.

Previous

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4.2 Survey 2: SMART indicators and output measures

The second instrument used in WP 6 to evaluate SIE contributions are specific, measurable, achievable, relevant and timely (SMART) indicators. Whereas the assessment in Survey 1 is based on the subjective perception of the different actors interviewed, SMART indicators aim to provide a more objective measure of the contributions of SIE(-initiatives). Examples of SMART indicators, which could be collected from SIE initiatives are displayed in Table 4 below.

As the identified SIE types differ considerably, it is likely that the nature of their contributions will also differ. The below list of SMART indicators should thus be considered as a starting point, that may be adjusted depending on the data which SIE initiatives can provide (cf. question 4 of Survey 1 above).

In addition to the impacts, we will also record the type of outputs which SIE-initiatives used to generate these impacts. This will allow us to verify, whether certain types of output are more suitable than others to generate an impact.

Data collection process:

WP6 Analysts/ WP3 Researchers: will email the SIE-representatives specified in Survey 1, question 4, and Excel-version of Survey 2 and ask them to fill-in the output measures and SMART indicators for their SIE-initiative and email back the responses to WP6 researchers who will store them in the SONNET Cloud:

SONNET cloud\06_WP6 success\06_Surveys\Survey 02

City partners will be asked to provide SMART indicators for their country and their city

Language: [Change the language](#)

Measuring Achievements

Thank you for starting the survey. In the SONNET research project, we study the aims and contributions of various energy-related initiatives/ projects throughout Europe. We would appreciate if you would take the time to answer the following questions about how your energy- related initiative/ project measures the achievement of its aims. Depending on the data you collect, the questions may take 15-45 minutes to answer. It would be great if you could answer the survey within the next week so we can use your responses in our work.

Some questions may be challenging to precisely answer. Just give us your best guess. There are no right or wrong answers.

Your answers will be treated confidentially and will only be accessed by researchers of the SONNET project. If you have any questions or concerns, please contact the person who send you the invitation for this survey.

Thank you for your support.

We would like to outline the survey data collection, storage and use for your approval before you start the survey. The personal data related to this survey includes your name, affiliated initiative/ project, and your email address. This data is used only for the survey invitation and tracking of survey completion. The research data is not stored with personal data, thus responses are not connected to individuals, and will be analyzed and presented in a way that does not allow someone to trace the responses back to an individual. Please refer to the information sheet provided in the invitation email for further information. Data collected through this survey is kept strictly confidential and will only be available to the research team. The data is stored on institutional servers which are only accessible to team members. At any time, you may contact us by email to view the data or ask for it to be withdrawn without having to give a reason.

Do you consent to the collection, storage and use of the data you provide in the survey as described above?

Yes I consent.

[Next](#)

In which year was ORGANISATION-NAME established?

[?](#) If not precisely known, please give your best estimate.

***What are the main participants of ORGANISATION-NAME? Here we refer to the main people involved in ORGANISATION-NAME, thus please identify these.**

**How many does ORGANISATION-NAME have at the moment?
If not precisely known, please give your best estimate.**

How many employees (in full-time equivalent) does ORGANISATION-NAME have at the moment?

[?](#) Only an integer value may be entered in this field.

[?](#) If not precisely known, please give your best estimate.

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***Does ORGANISATION-NAME have a website?**

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

How many times was the website of ORGANISATION-NAME visited in...?

2017	<input type="text"/>
2018	<input type="text"/>
2019	<input type="text"/>

What was the annual budget of ORGANISATION-NAME for 2019?

Only an integer value may be entered in this field.

The next question will ask you for the currency of this answer.

What is the currency of the budget entered?

Previous

Next

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The following questions will ask you about the different activities of ORGANISATION-NAME. Choose all answers that apply. If the question does not apply or is not relevant, please choose "none". If you choose "Other:" please specify in the text field.

***A) What activities does ORGANISATION-NAME do to reduce the energy consumption?**

- none
- provide general advice (e.g. information on consumption of different appliances).
- provide personalized advice (e.g. energy audit).
- grant discounts on new devices (e.g. more efficient heating).
- give financial support (e.g. loans).
- give financial rewards
- invest in retrofits
- invest in new devices
- give social incentives (e.g. reflect savings in reputation to community)
- Other:

***B) What activities does ORGANISATION-NAME do to increase renewable energy production?**

- none
- provide general advice (e.g. on existing support schemes)
- provide personalized advice (e.g. cost-benefit calculation for concrete investment location)
- give financial support (e.g. loans)
- give financial rewards
- invest in renewables production
- match renewable energy producers to buyers of certificates
- Other:

***C) What activities does ORGANISATION-NAME do to reduce the greenhouse gas emissions?**

- none
- activities to reduce consumption (such as listed in question A)
- activities to promote renewable energy production (such as listed in question B)
- invest in electromobility
- switch to electric or gas heating
- purchase certificates to compensate emissions
- Other:

***D) What activities does ORGANISATION-NAME do to promote trade between its members and other customers and regions?**

- none
- improve and/or create a regional market-place
- improve and/or create a national market-place
- create a connection to national electricity market operators
- maximize local consumption, rather than promoting trade
- Other:

***E) What activities does ORGANISATION-NAME do to increase the security of energy supply for its members?**

- none
- increase local production (such as listed in question B)
- increase local storage
- increase available back-up power
- Other:

***F) What activities does ORGANISATION-NAME do to reduce the price which its members pay for electricity?**

- none
- activities to reduce consumption (such as listed in question A)
- increase local production (such as listed in question B)
- reduce imports from the grid (such as listed in question C)
- use group purchasing to reduce prices
- sell flexibility/ available capacity
- facilitate local trade
- Other:

***G) What activities does ORGANISATION-NAME do to promote the development of new technologies?**

- none
- participate in pilot projects with new technologies
- invest in research and development
- facilitate exchange about best practices
- Other:

Previous

Next

The following questions ask about the measured impact of ORGANISATION-NAME in different areas as a result of their activities.

***Does ORGANISATION-NAME measure their impact on energy consumption?**

Choose one of the following answers

- Yes, by specifying the yearly percentage (%) reduction of energy consumption as a result of activities.
- Yes, with an alternative way to measure the yearly energy consumption reduction. For example, kWh.
- No, there is no impact and/or measure in this area.

Please specify the units of the alternative measure.

Annual consumption in kWh

The above-mentioned measurement had the following values in 2018 and 2019. If unknown, please leave blank.

	Value and Unit
2018	<input type="text"/>
2019	<input type="text"/>

***Does ORGANISATION-NAME measure their impact on renewable energy production?**

Choose one of the following answers

- Yes, by specifying how many kWh per year of energy ORGANISATION-NAME, or its participants, produced from renewable sources.
- Yes, with an alternative way to quantify the yearly impact on renewable energy production.
- No, there is no impact and/or measure in this area.

***Does ORGANISATION-NAME measure their impact on greenhouse gas emissions?**

Choose one of the following answers

- Yes, by specifying the reduction of (in tonnes) of CO2 per year as a result of activities.
- Yes, with an alternative way to measure the yearly CO2 reduction. (For example, transportation with bike instead of car)
- No, there is no impact and/or measure in this area

***Does ORGANISATION-NAME measure their impact on energy imports?**

Choose one of the following answers

- Yes, by specifying the percentage (%) of the total yearly electricity of the members of ORGANISATION-NAME bought from providers outside the initiative each year.
- Yes, with an alternative measure for the electricity bought from external providers. (For example, total kWh)
- No, there is no impact and/or measure in this area

***Does ORGANISATION-NAME measure their impact on energy exports?**

Choose one of the following answers

- Yes, by specifying the percentage (%) of the total yearly produced electricity members of ORGANISATION-NAME sold to customers outside the initiative each year.
- Yes, with an alternative measure for the electricity sold to external customers. (For example, total kWh)
- No, there is no impact and/or measure in this area.

***Does ORGANISATION-NAME measure their impact on supply security?**

Choose one of the following answers

- Yes, by specifying the total storage in kWh, as there is local electricity to provide continued supply in case of a power outage from the utility supplier on a winter day, for example.
- Yes, with an alternative measure for the local storage available during power outages. (For example, number of minutes of available power)
- No, there is no impact and/or measure in this area.

***Does ORGANISATION-NAME measure their impact on electricity price?**

Choose one of the following answers

- Yes, by specifying the average price per kWh of electricity for members of ORGANISATION-NAME for each year (including grid charges, taxes etc.).
- Yes, with an alternative measure for the average electricity price of customers. (For example, % of income paid for electricity)
- No, there is no impact and/or measure in this area.

***Does ORGANISATION-NAME measure their impact on innovation?**

Choose one of the following answers

- Yes, by specifying how many patents have been filed due to activities.
- Yes, with an alternative way of measuring the innovation generated from activities. (For example, number of new technologies developed)
- No, there is no impact and/or measure in this area.

Previous

Next

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***Are there additional ways you measure the achievement of ORGANISATION-NAME?**

- Yes, there are additional measures.
- There are no additional measures
- I don't know

In which additional ways do you measure the achievement of ORGANISATION-NAME?

Examples could be the number of events organized, the number of petitions signed, the number of articles published etc. Please specify the most relevant ways (max. 3) for which you have data available.

Measure 1:

Measure 2:

Measure 3:

Please let us know what you have measured in the last two years.

If you only have data for one of the years or if you don't know the value, just leave the space blank; You may use the comment field to provide further information about how the metric was calculated.

	2018	2019	Comment
Custom Metric	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Previous

Next

If you have any further information about the activities and impacts of ORGANISATION-NAME - such as an annual report, brochure, project presentation or other - feel free to upload the relevant document(s) here.

Please upload at most 10 files

Upload files

Previous

Submit

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4.3 Survey 3: SIE-participant views

The third instrument that is used in WP6 to evaluate the aims and contributions of SIE-initiatives is a survey among the participants of the SIE-initiative. This will enable SIE-initiatives to explore their aims from another perspective and collect ideas for improving their services.

Data collection process:

WP6 Analysts: will create an online version of Survey 3 using Lime-Survey. They will contact SIE-representatives specified in Survey 1 via email and ask them to circulate a link to the online-version of Survey 3 to (part of) their members; participants; partners; supporters; or supported groups. Although responses to Survey 3 do not contain personal / identifiable information, they will be stored on a password protected, GDPR compliant server in Germany (further infos see: <https://www.limesurvey.org/customer-support/frequently-asked-questions?view=faq&faqid=43>). Responses will be downloaded and stored in the SONNET Cloud:

SONNET cloud\06_WP6 success\06_Surveys\Survey 03

Language: English

Participants of energy-related initiatives and projects

Thank you for starting the survey. In the SONNET research project (running from 2019-2022), we study the aims and contributions of energy-related initiatives/projects throughout Europe. We would appreciate if you could take 15 minutes to answer the following questions about a specific project you are involved in. In order for us to use your responses for our research, it would be great if you could complete the survey latest by 31st December 2020.

Some questions may be challenging to answer precisely. If this is the case, just give us your best guess. There are no right or wrong answers.

Your answers will be treated confidentially and will only be accessed by researchers of the SONNET project. Only the aggregate results over several respondents will be reported, in an anonymized form that does not allow identification of individual respondents. If you have any questions or concerns, please contact the person who sent you the invitation for this survey.

Thank you for your support.

We would like to outline the survey data collection, storage and use for your approval before you start the survey. The personal data related to this survey include your name and your email address. This data is used only for the survey invitation and tracking of survey completion. The research data collected in the survey asks about basic socio-demographic information (such as age, gender, education, employment and living situation), your role within the initiative/ project that you are involved in, and your perception of specific environmental aims. Personal data are stored separately from the research data. Thus, responses are not connected to individuals, and will be analyzed and presented in a way that does not allow to trace responses back to an individual. Data collected through this survey is kept strictly confidential and will only be available to the research team. The data is stored on institutional servers which are only accessible to team members, and will be destroyed 10 years after the project ends. At any time, you may contact us by email to view the data or ask for it to be withdrawn without having to give a reason.

Do you consent to the collection, storage and use of the data you provide in the survey as described above?

Yes I consent.

Next

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***On behalf of which energy-related initiative/project are you answering the survey?**

Previous

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***How important are the following reasons for your decision to be involved in ORGANISATION-NAME?**

	Very important	Moderately important	Hardly important	Not important	I don't know
increase independence of energy supplies	<input type="radio"/>				
reduce energy bill for consumers	<input type="radio"/>				
improve quality of life	<input type="radio"/>				
increase the production from renewable energy sources	<input type="radio"/>				
reduce energy consumption	<input type="radio"/>				
increase energy efficiency	<input type="radio"/>				
improve social acceptance of renewable energy production	<input type="radio"/>				
reduce greenhouse gas emissions	<input type="radio"/>				
strengthen local community	<input type="radio"/>				
increase local economic development	<input type="radio"/>				
improve security of energy supply	<input type="radio"/>				
improve the transfer of knowledge in the energy sector.	<input type="radio"/>				
impact energy policy processes	<input type="radio"/>				
improve economic feasibility of renewable energy projects	<input type="radio"/>				
advocate for regional renewable energy projects	<input type="radio"/>				
increase trade of energy with neighbouring regions	<input type="radio"/>				
develop new renewable energy technologies	<input type="radio"/>				
provide support for other energy-related initiatives or projects	<input type="radio"/>				
reduce impact on the environment	<input type="radio"/>				

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How has ORGANISATION-NAME affected you with regard to the following aims? Please indicate all relevant impacts by ticking the box in the column.

ORGANISATION-NAME has:

	Reminded or made me aware of this aim.	Convinced me to support this aim.	Explained how I could contribute to this aim.	Made me contribute to this aim.	Not applicable
improve social acceptance of renewable energy production	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
increase independence of energy supplies	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
improve quality of life	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
advocate for regional renewable energy projects	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
reduce energy bill for consumers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
improve security of energy supply	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
increase energy efficiency	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
increase local economic development	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
provide support for other energy-related initiatives or projects	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
increase the production from renewable energy sources	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
improve the transfer of knowledge in the energy sector.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
increase trade of energy with neighbouring regions	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
reduce impact on the environment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
improve economic feasibility of renewable energy projects	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
develop new renewable energy technologies	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
reduce greenhouse gas emissions	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
reduce energy consumption	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
impact energy policy processes	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
strengthen local community	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Do you have any suggestions, how ORGANISATION-NAME could improve its contribution to the above aims?

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Hereafter you will find statements about different aspects of your personality. There are no right or wrong answers. Different people have different personalities and none is better or worse than others. They are just different. Please answer spontaneously and tick the answer that you feel best describes your personality.

***To what extent do you agree to the following statements describing your personality?**

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
My life would be better if I owned certain things I don't have.	<input type="radio"/>				
I admire people who own expensive homes, cars, and clothes.	<input type="radio"/>				
I like to own things that impress people.	<input type="radio"/>				
I'd be happier if I could afford to buy more things.	<input type="radio"/>				
I like a lot of luxury in my life.	<input type="radio"/>				
I try to keep my life simple, as far as possessions are concerned.	<input type="radio"/>				
It sometimes bothers me quite a bit that I can't afford to buy all the things I'd like.	<input type="radio"/>				
Buying things gives me a lot of pleasure.	<input type="radio"/>				
The things I own say a lot about how well I'm doing in life.	<input type="radio"/>				

***To what extent do you agree to the following statements describing your personality?**

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
My purchase habits are affected by my concern for our environment.	<input type="radio"/>				
I am willing to be inconvenienced in order to take actions that are more environmentally friendly.	<input type="radio"/>				
I am concerned about wasting the resources of our planet.	<input type="radio"/>				
I would describe myself as environmentally responsible.	<input type="radio"/>				
I consider the potential environmental impact of my actions when making many of my decisions.	<input type="radio"/>				
It is important to me that the products I use do not harm the environment.	<input type="radio"/>				

In which year did you start participating in ORGANISATION-NAME?

Format: yyyy

*How well do the following describe your current role/ activity in ORGANISATION-NAME?

	Very fitting description	Somewhat fitting description	Does not fit at all
Customer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Employee	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
App user	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Participant	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Member	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Supported institution	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Supporter	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Website visitor	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Manager	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please provide the best description for your role/activity in ORGANISATION-NAME, if it was not already mentioned above.

How old are you (in years)?

*Please indicate your gender.

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say
- Other

*Please indicate your status in your current primary residence.

- Married or living as a couple (with or without children)
- Living with parents or other relatives
- Living alone
- Living as a single parent
- Sharing the primary residence with non-family members
- Living in a hostel type accommodation, e.g., university dormitory, army base

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Including yourself, how many people of each age group live in your household?

i Only numbers may be entered in these fields.

Children under 6 years old

Children between 6 and 17 years old

Adults between 18 and 65 years old

Seniors more than 65 years old

*What is your highest level of education?

- No degree or certificate
- Trade/Vocational certificate or equivalent
- High school or equivalent
- Higher education degree or equivalent (College, University...)
- Don't know

*How would you best describe the area in which you live?

- Centre of a major town / city
- Suburban (fringes of a major town / city)
- Small town or village
- Isolated dwelling (Not in a town or village)

*What is your current employment status?

- Self-employed
- Employee (full time, part time or on temporary leave)
- Retired
- Homemaker - househusband/wife
- Seeking a job/unemployed
- Student
- Unable to work, e.g., disability
- Other:

***What is your household's approximate annual income, after tax? (Please include income from everyone in your household from all sources, including wages, government and company pensions and benefits, and investments dividends, rents)**

If you do not know the exact figure, please estimate.

- 1€ - 3 600€ (approx. 1€ - 300€ monthly)
- 3 601€ - 7 200€ (approx. 301€ - 600€ monthly)
- 7 201€ - 12 000€ (approx. 601€ - 1 000€ monthly)
- 12 001€ - 24 200€ (approx. 1 001€ - 2 000€ monthly)
- 24 201€ - 34 400€ (approx. 2 001€ - 2 850€ monthly)
- 34 401€ - 41 800€ (approx. 2 851€ - 3 500€ monthly)
- 41 801€ - 49 000€ (approx. 3 501€ - 4 100€ monthly)
- 49 001€ - 56 700€ (approx. 4 101€ - 4 700€ monthly)
- 56 701€ - 65 200€ (approx. 4 701€ - 5 450€ monthly)
- 65 201€ - 75 200€ (approx. 5 451€ - 6 350€ monthly)
- 75 201€ - 88 800€ (approx. 6 251€ - 7 400€ monthly)
- More than 88 800€ (more than approx. 7 400€ monthly)
- Don't know / no answer

Previous

Next

***Is your current primary residence ...**

- A detached house (with just 1 or 2 dwellings, e.g., house/apartments)
- A semi-detached house/terraced house (with just 1 - 2 dwellings)
- An apartment in a building with 3-6 dwellings
- An apartment in a building with 7-15 dwellings
- An apartment in a building with more than 15 dwellings

***Do you and/or other members of your household own your primary residence (with or without a mortgage)?**

- Yes, I/we own the house
- Yes, I/we own the apartment but not the entire building
- Yes, I/we own the apartment and the whole building (incl. other apartments I don't live in)
- No

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***To what extent do you agree with the following statements?**

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
To save energy is an important part of who I am.	<input type="radio"/>				
I think of myself as an energy conscious person	<input type="radio"/>				
I think of myself as someone who is very concerned with environmental issues	<input type="radio"/>				
Being environmentally friendly is an important part of who I am	<input type="radio"/>				

***Do any of your friends, family or colleagues buy energy-efficient products?**

Yes No

***How much influence do your family, friends and colleagues have on your decision to purchase - or not purchase - energy efficient products?**

- No influence
- Slight influence
- Some influence
- Moderate influence
- Large influence

***In general, what do you think your family's, friends' or colleagues' views would be of you purchasing energy efficient products?**

- Very unfavourable
- Somewhat unfavorable
- Indifferent
- Somewhat favorable
- Very favourable

***To what extent do you agree with the following statements?**

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
It makes me feel good to contribute to lowering global energy consumption.	<input type="radio"/>				
I feel responsible for making a contribution to lowering global energy consumption.	<input type="radio"/>				

Previous

Submit

5 EVALUATION METHODS

We will analyze the results from the surveys using the methodological approaches which are described in the following sections in more detail:

- **Rankings:** to sort policy aims by average importance, or to sort (types of) SIE-initiative by their support for a specific policy aim
- **Correlations:** to detect dependencies between the importance of aims, the level of contributions and explanatory variables, such as the SIE-field, country or measurement approach that was chosen to quantify these variables.
- **Regressions:** to quantify the effect size of relevant explanatory variables on the importance of aims or the perceived level of contributions in case of a sufficiently large sample size

We will illustrate each of these approaches using hypothetical data for a concrete research question.

5.1 Averages and Rankings

Our first step of analysis will be to produce descriptive statistics in the form of the average /min /max importance of different policy aims, or the average /min /max perceived contribution to different policy aims for each of the surveys and each of the policy aims. Ranking these values in ascending or descending order will allow us to answer questions such as the importance of different policy goals for SIE-initiatives, or to rank different SIE-initiatives by their contribution to a particular policy goal. This will be the input for the goal alignment map.

Example:

Research Question: How important are the EU policy goals for the SIE-initiatives?

Result: The following chart shows a ranking of policy goals by their average importance for different SIE-Initiatives. For the (illustrative) numbers below, the ranking shows that SIE-initiatives care more about their own goals than for the EU Policy goals.

5.2 Pairwise correlations

As a second step, we will use pairwise correlations to discover potential dependencies between different variables. As illustrated by the examples below, this may include a large number of different variable combinations, ranging from correlations between the importance of and the contribution to different aims to correlations between either of these variables and different control variables such as the country, the SIE-field, and correlations between the answers to the same question in different surveys. While pairwise correlations themselves do not allow us to determine the effect size, they may provide a first indication of answers to different research questions and help to guide the selection of independent variables for the regression analysis in the last step that would allow us to answer those questions in a statistically more robust way.

Example 1:

Research Question: What is the relationship between the perceived importance of and the perceived contribution to different aims?

Results: The following chart shows the correlation between perceived importance of different aims (x-axis) and the perceived contributions to the same aim (y-axis) for each of the aims that were assessed by a single researcher. The size of the bubbles corresponds to the number of times the same combination of importance rating and contribution rating appeared. Ratings for EU-Policy goals have a red circle. The (illustrative) numbers in this chart suggest that SIE-initiatives seem to make a larger contribution to those aims, which they perceive to be important.

Example 3:

Research Question: How well do researchers predict the importance of different aims for the SIE-initiatives?

Result: The following chart shows the correlation between the importance of different aims for an SIE initiative as perceived by the researcher (x-axis) or the SIE-representative (y-axis). The size of the bubbles corresponds to the number of times the same combination of average importance ratings appeared. Ratings for EU-Policy goals have a red circle. The (illustrative) numbers in this chart show that there is a reasonable – though not perfect - correlation between the importance of different policy aims as perceived by researchers vs. SIE-representatives, which would confirm the working hypothesis. This would suggest that researchers are able to see which aims are important for an SIE-initiative. The numbers also show, that researchers make a stronger distinction between important and unimportant aims (using importance ratings between 1 and 4) than the representatives of SIE-initiative who only use ratings between 3 and 4, potentially due to social desirability bias.

5.3 Multi-variate regressions

As a last step of the analysis, we will perform multi-variate regressions to detect the impact, which different independent variables could have on the importance of and the contribution to different policy aims. By contrast to the bivariate correlations from the previous section, this would allow us to determine the magnitude of the impact from different independent variables in a statistically more robust way, i.e. while controlling for the impact of the other independent variables. However, the number of independent variables that we can include as controls in the regression will depend on the number of respondents and may thus be severely limited.

Example:
$$PC_a = \alpha \cdot F + \beta \cdot C + \gamma \cdot P + \epsilon$$

Research Question: What is the *relative importance* of the previously mentioned factors as determinants for the contribution of an SIE-initiative to a particular policy goal?

Approach: To answer the above question we could run a multi-variate regression of the contribution of SIE-initiatives to the policy goal (PC_a) as a function of the SIE-field (F), to which the initiative belongs, the country (C), in which it is located and the type of respondent (R), who makes the assessment:

6 WORK PLAN AND KEY DATES

The table below describes the current workplan for WP6, including **closing dates for data collection**, and the dates for **meetings and discussions** and submission of **final deliverables**.

Table 9: Work-plan and key dates.

When?	Where?	What is done?	Who is in charge?
November 1st 2020	Via Email	Start sending invitations for WP6 survey 03 (surveys 01 and 02 are already running)	WP3 Researchers WP2 Researchers
31st December 2020	Online	Deadline for survey responses to be used in preliminary analysis.	WP3 Researchers
December 2020 to January 2021	-	Preliminary goal alignment analysis	WP6 Researchers
20th -23rd January 2021	Disentis/ Online conference	Discuss preliminary results of the goal alignment analysis and the evaluation scheme the conference in Disentis (or online).	WP6 Researchers
31st March 2021	Online	Deadline for survey responses to be used in final analysis.	WP3 Researchers
May 14th 2021	Via Email	Circulate goal alignment analysis (D24) for review	WP6 Researchers
May 28th 2021	Via Email	Submit review comments for goal alignment analysis (D24)	WP6 Reviewers(?)
June 11th 2021	Via Email	Submit revise goal alignment analysis (D24)	WP6 Researchers
July 1st 2021	Via Email	Circulate results of evaluation scheme (D25) for review	WP6 Researchers
July 2021	TBC	Discuss results of goal alignment and evaluation scheme at Sonnet workshop	WP6 Researchers
August 2021	Via Email	Submit revised results of evaluation scheme (D25)	WP6 Researchers

Appendix 1: Working Process Summary

Work Flow for WP3 researchers supporting the WP6 surveys

Follow the flow chart below from top to bottom (which would be chronological order) for each of the organizations which you interview

Working Process from the Perspective of a WP3 Researcher

Where to find things

